

RECENT INNOVATIONS AND THEIR ROLE IN THE MODERNIZATION OF PRESCHOOL AND PRIMARY EDUCATION IN UKRAINE**Polishuk L.,***Senior Lecturer,***Burdenyuk R.***Professor Assistant,***Gvozdii S.***Doctor of Science in Pedagogy, Professor,***Pienov V.***Candidate of Science in Pedagogy, Associate Professor,**Department of Human Physiology, Health and Safety and Natural Science Education**Odesa I.I. Mechnikov National University, Odesa, Ukraine***Abstract**

The features and content of recent innovations and innovative technologies in preschool and primary education in Ukraine are discussed. The significance and necessity of their introduction into the educational process are analyzed. Also, the details of the reform of primary education in Ukraine and other education-related reforms are discussed. The existing innovative educational technologies and their implication based on a child personality development features are also discussed. The focus is on the issues of inclusive education for children with special educational needs. New mechanisms for the development and professional growth of teachers are proposed. Priorities for further development of the education in Ukraine have been identified. The New Ukrainian School (NUS) is described as a key reform of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine. Introduction of some innovative technologies such as health-oriented education, game technologies, media and communication technologies, and personality-oriented technologies in preschool and primary education is proposed.

Keywords: teacher, technologies, innovations, modernization, competencies, education transformation, preschool, primary school, inclusive education, primary school reform, New Ukrainian School (NUS).

Introduction. As a country aiming at joining the European Union, Ukraine strives towards building fast-growing sustainable economy which can be achieved by considerable and even radical transformation of the country's education in general and preschool and primary school education in particular. Although the systemic transformation of the preschool and primary school education in Ukraine has already begun and certain developments could already be seen, there is still a long way to go. The main instruments of the innovation introduction into the preschool and primary school education are: active search of ways to improve the educational process in general; healthy competition between educational institutions; incentive factors aiming at teachers' improvement of the quality educational services they provide etc.

The aim of the article is to determine the features and content of innovations and innovative technologies of the educational process in preschool and primary education in Ukraine. To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set: to determine the need for innovative processes in educational practice, to find out which changes have already taken place in preschool education, to analyze the content the reform of the country's primary education and to outline the main priorities in education transformation.

Discussion. Nowadays, everything is changing quickly. That also concerns the educational process, which means, that a lot of attention should to be paid to innovative educational technologies in order to keep up. It is the use of the latest innovative technologies in the learning process that necessitates the reform of preschool and primary education. Much more attention is now paid to personal development, so the main task of

teachers is to develop the creative potential of participants of the educational process, combining traditions of the national school with new ideas coming from abroad.

In general, the "innovation" concept means something new, novelty, change. In accordance with the pedagogical process, innovation involves the introduction of new content, methods and forms of teaching and education, the new, more advanced and effective forms of interaction between students and a teacher. In our opinion, innovations do not simply appear from nowhere, they come as a result of extensive scientific research, pedagogical experience of individual teachers. It should be noted that one of the basic principles of modern education is the idea of its continuity which means that the process of education, training and formation of personality begins at birth and lasts a lifetime. Currently, the state recognizes that the main stages of physical, mental and social development of a child's personality are the following: infants (up to 1 year of age), early age (1-3 years) and preschool age (3-6/7 years). That is why preschool education in Ukraine is a mandatory primary part of the system of continuing education [4]. Thus, the system of preschool education in Ukraine is changing simultaneously in two directions: from the legal framework to practical actions.

As a result of the implementation of the recent Law of Ukraine "About preschool education" the following changes took place:

1. Personality development periods:

Was: infants, toddlers, preschool age, middle school age, and older preschool age [3];

Now: Infants, toddlers (1-3 years), preschool age (3-6/7 years), younger (3-4), middle (4-5), and older (5-6/7) preschool age [2].

2. Changes have been made in the list of possible means of obtaining preschool education in Ukraine:

Was:

- preschool educational institutions, regardless of subordination, types and forms of ownership;
- child's family (until the child reaches the age of 5);
- education provided by individuals with high moral qualities who have an appropriate university pedagogical education and are licensed to provide preschool educational services [3].

Now:

- preschool education institutions, regardless of subordination, types and forms of ownership;
- structural subdivisions of legal entities of private and public law, including educational institutions;
- child's family - according to the family (home) type of preschool education;
- education provided by individuals with university pedagogical education and / or professional qualifications of a teacher, including those who provide their services as self-employed professionals;
- small businesses which provide educational services as their main activity [4].

3. The preschool educational institutions received the authority to:

- plan their own activities and develop strategies;
- design their educational programs;
- hire their own employees;
- create, reorganize and discontinue their structural subdivisions (branches, groups) [4].

Despite the large number of preschool institutions in Ukraine, children in different regions have unequal access to them: in some regions there are open vacancies in preschools, but in most other regions of Ukraine the situation is opposite - there is a lack of jobs. And that means that not all parents who have a need or desire to place their child in preschool educational institution can do so in timely manner. The corresponding imbalance and lack of teacher's jobs has long been one of the sources of corruption at various levels in the preschool education system in Ukraine. Thus, the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine has introduced the so-called "electronic queue" - an open and transparent service for enrollment in preschool education, which provides equal opportunities for all children regardless of their parents' financial situation in all Ukrainian regions [4].

Further innovations concern mainly practical aspects:

1. Automated on-line registration of preschool children. At this time the on-line registration system in Ukraine is already active. Parents just need to choose an educational institution for their kid and register with it. The system provides free access to the queue; one child can be registered with queues to 1 to 5 kindergartens at the same time with a possibility to keep track of the progress in each queue. The main purpose of the system is to eliminate or reduce corruption in preschool institutions. In order to register with the system parents

first need to choose an available kindergarten and fill out the form, which contains first and last name of the child, his/her date of birth and the birth certificate number, parental phone number. Parents can choose 1 or 5 institutions to register with and then click on "Submit" button. If the registration is successful, the application status changes to "Registered in the queue". The date and time of registration cannot be changed. In case of a vacancy opening the application status changes to "There is a possibility of enrollment", and a place will be offered in the selected kindergarten or another institution nearby. Parents will also be sent a notification to their e-mail address; they are expected to submit the necessary documents for admission within 30 days. If the document package is not submitted timely, the queue is canceled automatically. In the regions where kindergarten shortage is significant, parents can register with the system right after the birth of their child if they do not plan to move to a different region. Otherwise, early registration is not recommended [4].

2. Inclusive education is one of the greatest challenges faced by Ukrainian education system. The main reasons for that are: the deteriorating health of children, the desire of children with special needs to receive education in the same environment and the same conditions as other kids. It is a process of addressing the diverse needs of students by ensuring their participation in learning, cultural activities and community life. In other words, it is a way of education when students with special educational needs learn in the general educational environment provided locally. This is an alternative to the current special institution system, in which such children are kept and educated separately from other children, or home and individual education. Inclusive education in a broad sense implies the creation of equal opportunities for all categories of children in Ukraine. None of them should feel different - and this is the main task of the inclusive education [9].

Recently Ukraine has adopted the term "children with special educational needs", it is being used for children under 18 who need additional educational, medical and social support to improve health, development, learning and socialization. This category includes children with permanent or temporary disabilities [19]. That is why new inclusive groups with no more than 3 children with special educational needs were created in preschool educational institutions in Ukraine, as well as new positions - educator of inclusive group, assistant educator of inclusive group and practical psychologist of preschool educational institutions of inclusive group [5].

As an example, a modern inclusive resource center was opened in the city of Yuzhny in Odesa region in 2019. And now, rehabilitation and correction of the development of local children aged 2 to 18 with special educational needs is carried out here. The center is well equipped to provide physical therapy, psychological relief, psychological and pedagogical assistance and assessment. Based on the results of a comprehensive assessment of the child's development, the center's specialists provide assistance to the child, and can refer him/her to an educational institution [6].

According to the statistics, in the last few years alone, the number of students with special educational needs studying in regular schools along with their peers has increased by 60%. According to the Minister of Education and Science of Ukraine, thanks to funding from the state budget, a significant number of children used correctional services; a number of Inclusive Resource Centers (IRC) have been created and equipped. In recent years, 1,220 such centers have been established throughout the country. From 2019, unrestricted access to the 1st floor and different facilities of 11,560 or 74% of all secondary educational institutions has been established by installing: 10781 ramps, 3664 call buttons, 2864 information boards, 51 elevators or lifts, 746 specially designed toilets, etc. It should be noted that the problem of accessibility of children with special educational needs to schools and other educational institutions remains a problem. However, the situation is gradually changing for the better every year [7].

3. The Government has approved an action plan for the creation of additional places in educational institutions for preschool children for 2021. During the opening ceremony of the Forum of All-Ukrainian Preschool Week "Preschool Education of Ukraine 30", Minister of Education and Science of Ukraine Serhiy Shkarlet reported almost 20,000 additional created places in preschool institutions in Ukraine during the years 2020 and 2021. Over this period, the number of preschool institutions has increased by 572, almost 20,000 additional places for kids have been created, and 88 institutions were opened as long as another 200 private institutions. Of course, the leaders are the city of Kyiv - 102, Kyiv region - 53, the city of Odesa - 23 institutions, etc. [1].

4. The project of a new mechanism of financing of preschool institutions - "Money follows the child" has been implemented. This project is reported to have started working in January 2019 in some preschools in the city of Kyiv. It should be noted that experience of Sweden, Canada, England, etc. was extensively used in the implementation of this mechanism. In those countries parents of 3-4-year-old children receive special vouchers from the state and use them at their own discretion. As a result, it is not the educational institution being financially supported, but the child itself. The main advantages of this new for Ukraine financial standard "Money follows the child" are: equal access to quality education; reduction of the queue to preschool institutions, optimizing of a studying group size; improving educational services in kindergartens on a competitive basis; fair distribution of finances. The funding rate per child is now UAH 2,200. However, if the parents change the educational institution, the money goes with the child and get transferred to the new institution in accordance with the services provided [14].

It is equally important to understand the reform of primary education. The creation of the New Ukrainian School (NUS) is a key reform of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine. It applies to the whole system of education, starting from primary school. The main goal of the NUS is to create a school pleasant to study in and which provides students not with

knowledge only, but also with the actual ability to apply it in their professional career.

The NUS concept consists of nine components:

- The new education program aimed at formation of competencies necessary for successful self-realization in society.
- Motivated, creative and highly skilled teacher.
- Systemic education that shapes values.
- Effective leadership and decentralization that provides schools with great amount of autonomy.
- Science of pedagogy based upon partnership between student, teacher and parents.
- Student-centered educational process.
- New school structure that allows obtaining knowledge and competencies.
- Equitable distribution of public funds, which ensures equal access of all children to quality education.
- Modern educational environment that provides conditions, tools and technologies for educating students, teachers and parents in and out of school [17].

There are a lot of innovations in the new structure of primary school in Ukraine. The law "On Education" establishes three levels of complete general secondary education: primary education (duration - 4 years); basic secondary education (duration - 5 years); specialized secondary education obtained in lyceums or colleges etc. (duration - 3 years). According to the law, total duration of complete secondary education has increased to 12 years.

Primary education. As a rule, children begin their primary education at the age of six. Children with special needs can start whenever considered fit. In every primary school the quality standards of education, especially in foreign language, have been raised. Primary education is provided by the single standard in all educational institutions - now all schools are the same in order to avoid social stratification of children in primary school age. Primary education in the new school is divided into 2 cycles: adaptive game (grades 1-2) and basic (grades 3-4).

The first cycle of primary education helps students in getting used to school life featuring the following aspects:

- educational tasks and time for their completion are determined individually;
- educational material could be integrated into the content of related subjects;
- the amount of homework is limited, there is no homework on weekends;
- learning is organized by gaming methods both in the classroom and outside;
- teacher has a freedom to choose among different educational programs within the educational standard;
- descriptive evaluation is introduced, traditional marks are not being used.

Teacher's task is to maintain confidence and motivation in each student.

In the second cycle of primary education, students develop a sense of responsibility and independence:

- methods which teach students to make an independent choice, to connect obtained knowledge with real life are recommended;

- teaching by subject is introduced, learning of certain subjects is evaluated.

Academic achievements of each student at the end of the primary education must meet the standard of education. The State Final Attestation (STA) of primary education is carried out only to monitor the quality of educational services provided by different institutions. In primary school and lyceum, there will be no more than 8 compulsory subjects for one class. At the same time, special attention in the educational process is paid to the study of the state language. This is supposed to lay the basis of conscious self-determination of the student as an individual, family and society member, his/her ability to be tolerant and understanding of people. Different schools will be able to design Educational programs (ED) independently (autonomously), as well as create curricula and programs in separate subjects in accordance with the current standards of secondary education, choose textbooks, methods of teaching and education, develop training facilities. However, the autonomy of the educational institutions implies their higher level of responsibility. Accordingly, the founders of the school will control the educational and financial and economic activities of the institution and under the terms of the contract will appoint the head of the school. The head will be elected on a competitive basis for up to five years and will be able to be elected for no more than two terms. In addition, the school's responsibility before the society for the quality of education will be increased. In addition, state control, such as inspections, will replace the public-state system of quality assurance in education [12, p.25-26].

There should be comfort in everything for a primary school student, because primary school is supposed to create for such children a model of their further education. It is recommended to equip the modern, New Ukrainian School (NUS) with furniture that meets certain requirements:

- safety (matte surface of the tabletop; no sharp corners, unpleasant odors; installation of devices that prevent floor damage);
- ergonomics (availability of furniture in sets (desk/table + chair) that best fit certain age groups; rounded corners of counter tops, backs and seats);
- dimensions and shapes (tables in the form of a trapezoid, triangle or other, which provide a quick transformation into different shapes for group work);
- strength (resistance to approved detergents and disinfectants);
- color (light warm shades of yellow, green, blue, beige, not too bright);
- aesthetics (modern design; compliance with the style of the general arrangement of the room, attractive appearance);
- weight (no more than 10 kg for a table/desk and 4 kg for a chair).

In general, the educational space is organized in such a way that the teacher can observe the activities of children in all possible groups, and students have enough storage for personal belongings and move around safely [10].

Also, a new State Standard for Primary General Education has been introduced. It prohibits any form of discrimination, presumption of a talent in all students and their equal access to education. According to the Standard, between 2nd and 3rd academic hours it is recommended to engage students in gaming activities preferably outdoors. At the end of each educational quarter there is a correctional week intended to overcome student academic differences, where the Standard provides for integrated learning in primary school: fluency in the state language; mathematical competence; competencies in the field of natural sciences, engineering and technology; innovation; environmental competence; information and communication competence; cultural competence [11].

The State Standard of Primary Education also requires development of certain key skills in primary students: reading comprehension; ability to express personal opinion verbally and in writing; critical and systematic thinking; creativity; ability to logically justify personal point; initiative; risks assessment; decision making; ability to manage personal emotions; ability to cooperate with other people.

There are also new rules for enrollment into 1st grade. The child has the right, but not the obligation, to study at a local educational institution. His/her right is guaranteed by the Law of Ukraine "On Education". According to the second and third paragraphs of the Article 13 of the Law of Ukraine "On Education", every person has the right to receive primary and basic secondary education in an educational institution closest to the person's place of residence. This guarantee is implemented through Part 7 of Article 18 of the Law of Ukraine "On General Secondary Education", according to which "Children living in the area of a certain school have a right for a primary enrollment into this school." If parents want to send their child to a primary school that is not assigned to their place of residence, they can do so. In such a case they need to apply for enrollment into the selected schools and such an enrollment can be granted based on vacancy availability. Children are admitted to the vacancies based on the results of a draw, which can be held on June 5 to 10, the selection is random; the draw must be transparent and public.

Thus, the priority tasks of pedagogical teams that are supposed to introduce innovations in preschool and primary schools are: analysis of educational innovations recognized as effective by domestic and world pedagogical science; monitoring of innovations that are effectively developed and implemented by different pedagogical teams; to create a database of implemented pedagogical innovations in preschool and primary educational institutions; development of recommendations on the innovations implementation [18].

Thus, the new content of primary education in Ukraine is defined:

- The State Standard of Primary Education approved, based on the competence approach, according to which 448,6 thousand first-graders started studying on September 1, 2018;

- Standard educational programs are approved for grades 1-4 of general secondary education institutions [14].

Educational environment for the New Ukrainian School is updated by purchasing of:

- computer equipment (9.5 thousand interactive projectors, 19.2 thousand laptops, 8 thousand tablets/net books, 16.5 thousand multi-functional devices, etc.);
- furniture (364,223 single student sets, 9,2 thousand double student sets, 6,9 thousand sets for teachers, 77, 1 thousand furniture for recreation areas);
- didactic materials (361.8 thousand books, 57.8 thousand natural objects, 164.3 thousand models, 16.8 thousand musical instruments, etc.) [15].

Anti-bullying, inclusive education and washroom accessibility are recognized as some of the key components of every Ukrainian student's well-being. Quality education is considered impossible without them. That is why, from 2019, the Ministry of Education and Science has been working on the development of anti-bullying programs, improving the field of inclusive education and updating all school washrooms.

In addition, new mechanisms have been developed for the development and professional growth of teachers. One of the most important of them is a voluntary certification of teachers. The main purpose of this certification is to identify and stimulate highly professional teachers who extensively use the new educational technologies and methods of competency-based learning and promote their dissemination. The digitalization of education has been started in rural schools. The National Educational Platform was launched in a test mode in 2019 - a digital educational system, which houses real electronic textbooks with virtual 3D materials that teachers can compose at will, scans of textbooks, interactive laboratories, forums for teachers' communication and more. In order for every school, including rural, to have access to this system, in the budget of Ukraine for 2019 more than 1 billion UAH was directed towards purchase of computers and the Internet access for schools that do not have it yet [14].

It should be emphasized, that in order to successfully develop children's creativity, a modern educator must be a creative person itself, the teacher must possess:

1. Ability to generate innovative ideas;
2. Flexibility - the ability to come up with a variety of ideas;
3. Originality - the ability to respond to non-standard stimuli;
4. Ability to improve the object by adding details;
5. Ability to solve problems, to analyze and synthesize.

Also, innovative technologies in preschool pedagogy should include health technologies, game technologies, information and communication technologies, personality-oriented technologies. In our opinion, every teacher should be a creator of innovations, because personal and professional qualities together with creativity, knowledge and appropriate skills help to fulfill their main goal - to raise healthy, creative and productive generation. It also defines the task of further development of educator's personality, a highly qualified teacher who is able to generate new ideas, develop

skills and desire to work independently on the development of their own individuality [8, p.233-234] The education system should aim to foster a "man of culture". A person, who not just obtains knowledge mechanically, but perceives it creatively - is a person of culture.

We see the main directions of educational transformation as follows:

- first of all, education should be a practice of freedom, first in understanding and discussing life situations, and then in socially significant actions;
- the main goal of pedagogical efforts should be student's personality, an integral element of which is critical thinking;
- dialogue is a valuable tool of achieving this goal, and the key component is the ability to communicate and reflect [16, p.47-48].

Conclusions. Younger generation is the driving force of social change and progress in any country. Currently, thanks to professional teachers in primary and secondary educational institutions in Ukraine, children receive the basics of communication of psychological and physical development, which contribute to their further socialization and adaptation. Innovative technologies of teaching, development and education in the system of preschool education in Ukraine are becoming the keys to restructuring the education system. In order for these innovations to be effective and productive, it is necessary to understand the importance of educators in this process, choose appropriate methods of organizing work with children that meet state standards of preschool education. It is important to value and foster child's personality as the key to the meaningful and productive life. The war brought adjustments to the development of preschool and primary education in Ukraine. Most children were left without the opportunity to attend pre-schools and schools. There is a lot of educational technologies already developed to this day, so the question arises - which technology is the most effective and can be used in different conditions? Every teacher should answer this question for itself on the basis of their own knowledge, experience and expertise keeping in minds the main goal of any innovation in teaching - more healthy, adaptive and efficient personality.

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